

Timber Construction Details with AI Support: Design Methods for Early Planning Phases

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Abstract

Timber construction companies often rely on pre-drawn catalogues rather than parametric design methods for designing construction details. While parametric design could save significant time and effort, its adoption in the industry has been slow due to the limited availability of expertise required to develop complex parametric models among architects and timber engineers.

This thesis investigates methods for automated generation of construction drawings, with the aim to understand neural network learning processes and develop a digital tool capable of autonomously designing construction details.

The capabilities of rule-based methods, such as Grasshopper, are described. Conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs) were selected as the AI method due to their ability to generate highly detailed images. A synthetic dataset of 60,000 unique wall-section variants was created while ensuring technical functionality and realism. Although an ML-optimized dataset approach was successfully tested, it was ultimately not pursued further.

Technical challenges emerged during tool development. Training was constrained to CPU resources, leading to instability. The longest training session on a test dataset (CIFAR-10) lasted only 4 epochs before automatic termination. As a result, training cGANs on the wall-section dataset was not attempted. Establishing a well-configured training environment is crucial before meaningful results can be obtained and a more in-depth assessment of cGAN capabilities can be conducted.

Despite these challenges, cGANs demonstrate strong potential for understanding complex relationships in data, including those in construction drawings. In the future, it may be possible to generate construction drawings using plain text prompts. Such pretrained AI models could significantly lower the skill barrier associated with parametric design in the building industry. The cGAN architecture for 2D drawing can also be adapted for 3D construction. However, achieving this in either 2D or 3D will require the availability of real-world construction drawings to effectively train cGANs.

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List of Terminologies

AI	Artificial Intelligence Explained in Chapter 3.3
AISB	Society for the Study of Artificial Intelligence and Simulation of Behaviour.
API	Application Programming Interface A set of rules and protocols that define how software components interact and exchange data.
CAD	Computer-Aided Design The process of using software, which allows to create digital design models in 2D and 3D.
cGAN	Conditional Generative Adversarial Network A variant of GAN. Explained in Chapter 4.2.2
CIFAR-10	A dataset consisting of 60,000 labelled 32×32 colour images in 10 classes, widely used for training and evaluating model performance.
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network A type of Deep Neural Network, widely used for Computer Vision Explained in Chapter 4.2.
CPU	Central Processing Unit The primary processor in a computer, for general-purpose computations.
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture An API developed by NVIDIA that enables developers to utilize GPU capabilities for high-performance parallel computing.
DL	Deep Learning Explained in Chapter 3.5
DNN	Deep Neural Network Explained in Chapter 3.5
ETH-Zürich	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich A leading university known for its excellence in research, innovation and teaching.
FFNN	Feedforward Neural Network A simple type of Neural Network

GAN	Generative Adversarial Network A concept in which two neural networks compete against each other, enhancing each other's performance. A sub-category of this is a cGAN, which is described in Chapter 4.2.2.
GH	Grasshopper Explained in Chapter 4.1.1
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit A specialized processor designed for efficient parallel computations.
ML	Machine Learning Explained in Chapter 3.4
NPZ	A NumPy file format that efficiently stores multiple NumPy arrays and allows quick data loading.
NURBS	Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines A mathematical model for representing curves and surfaces in CAD software.
RAM	Random Access Memory A type of computer memory that temporarily stores data for quick access, allowing for efficient processing.
RGB	Red-Green-Blue colour space The RGB colour space is a type of additive colour definition, containing values for red, green, and blue.
Rhino	Rhinoceros A non-industry-specific CAD software. Further explained in Chapter 4.1.1
Sub-D	Subdivision Surface A method for representing smooth surfaces based on a coarse polygon mesh in CAD software.
UCEM	A university college in England specialized in distance learning with a focus on real estate and construction.
VAE	Variational Autoencoder A type of DNN, possible to use for image generation.
WSL	Windows Subsystem for Linux Enables running a Linux environment directly on Windows.

1 Introduction

This bachelor's thesis is based on my recent paper "Die Zukunft der parametrischen Planung: Welches Potenzial hat parametrische Planung in der Holzbaubranche?" (translated: The Future of Parametric Planning: What Potential Does Parametric Planning Have in the Timber Construction Industry?) (Rosin 2025). The paper highlights several challenges that hinder the development of parametric design, particularly in the timber construction industry.

Many timber construction companies still rely on pre-drawn catalogues of construction details, which they adapt for new projects. Parametric design, for example a Grasshopper script for designing a construction detail, could already today save significant time and effort. However, timber construction companies have been slow to adopt it. This is to be expected, as the skill of creating parametric definitions has not been widely adopted by architects and timber engineers.

This bachelor's thesis takes the automatic generation of construction drawings for timber construction as a case study. A long-term goal is to develop a digital tool capable of understanding and designing architectural details without companies being reliant on specialists. The primary focus is on exploring AI-based approaches to address these challenges. Compared to rule-based methods, where details are defined through complex (Grasshopper) scripts, AI-based approaches could offer significant advantages. Among other things, they reduce dependence on specialists who would otherwise need to create and modify rule sets manually. Instead, an AI model could autonomously define the relationships between building components by learning from training data. Furthermore, such a model could adapt to the specific construction and design preferences of the company. It could also improve over time by learning from incorrect outputs.

Additionally, a digital tool based on AI could enable individuals without experience in parametric design to generate draft construction details in the early planning phases. For this purpose, a conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN) has been selected as a promising representative of AI-based methods for generating detailed images. Accordingly, for rule-based methods it will be the commonly used parametric design tool Grasshopper. The focus of this thesis is to develop an initial understanding of the learning processes of neural networks and the practical development of the proposed digital tool.

The thesis begins by introducing deep neural networks (DNNs) and their ability to learn from complex data. This is followed by an introduction to the methods used in the study. Next, the process of developing a dataset and a digital tool is explained. The results are then presented and analysed in the conclusion. Finally, possible directions for further research are discussed.

2 Current Issues in Parametric Design

From October 2023 to March 2024, I completed an internship at a nationally operating Swiss timber construction company. During this time, I observed several issues that hinder the full potential of parametric design in timber construction. Additionally, I conducted several interviews on this topic with leading researchers and supporters of parametric design, including Hanno Stehling from Design-to-Production, Prof. Philipp Eversmann from the University of Kassel, and Aurèle L. Gheyselinck, a doctoral candidate at ETH Zürich. For full transcripts read Rosin (2025).

The mentioned challenges are not limited to timber construction companies but extend to parametric design in general.

The main problem lies in the lack of know-how among workers to create logical algorithms that represent, for example, timber construction details. Many companies rely on detail catalogues containing a broad variety of pre-drawn details, which are then adapted to fit new projects. Additionally, component-sections are not connected to the connection details, leading to inconsistent and redundant information (Rosin 2025).

Some larger architecture and construction companies have begun hiring specialists in parametric algorithms to enhance and automate their workflows. Despite this, each type of construction detail still requires a unique parametric definition to be developed. As a result, companies become highly dependent on one or a few specialists who can modify or create these parametric definitions. This dependence creates significant risks, as the departure of these key people could disrupt the company's ability to work with parametric design (Rosin 2025).

Moreover, there are currently only few professionals with expertise in parametric design, as only recently some universities have started including it as a required part of construction-related programs. Even among students who complete these mandatory courses, many do not choose to continue working with parametric design, suggesting that it is not yet widely embraced (Rosin 2025).

3 Context

In this chapter provides an overview of the context in which this thesis is situated. The connection between Generative Design, Parametric Design, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL) is described.

3.1 Generative Design

Generative design is a process where a design is created by software based on small bits of input data. This input data must be prepared in the correct format and can include elements such as "design goals, materials, cost constraints, and other data points." Using generative design, numerous possible design variants can be explored, allowing the most suitable option to be selected (Autodesk n.d.). Afterward, the generated option is selected and further refined. The result of the generative process is not meant to be a perfect solution but rather one that closely matches the desired outcome. This output can then be manually fine-tuned by humans to achieve the final result (Ashton 2024a).

For a generative design algorithm to function effectively, the input data must be of high quality, and individuals working with a generative design tool need to possess the necessary skills to use it proficiently. However, the building industry is currently facing a skill shortage, which presents a challenge that must be addressed (Ashton 2024a). This aligns with expert interviews conducted in 2024 (Rosin 2025).

3.2 Parametric Design

Parametric design is closely related to generative design, and the two are often used together, making them difficult to differentiate. However, their objectives differ: generative design focuses on developing "a solution for a specific issue" while "parametric design [is creating] opportunities for customisation". Parametric design relies heavily on the human designer to control the parametric functions, whereas generative design tools operate with a much higher degree of autonomy (Ashton 2024b).

Ursula Frick from Blumer Lehmann defines parametric design as the programming of 3D models. In parametric design, a set of rules, such as construction principles, is defined as a function that describes the building component in various dimensions. This approach allows the component to be specified simply by inputting the required parameters into the parametric function (Blumer Lehmann n.d.).

The UCEM defines parametric design as "an algorithm-based technique that develops complex and customised components, products and structures. In the process, architects identify a set of parameters which influence the building's design" which can be modified later if needed (Ashton 2024b).

3.3 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Many official organizations operating in the field of AI, such as the Society for the Study of Artificial Intelligence and Simulation of Behaviour (AISB), reference a definition provided by Prof. John McCarthy (AISB 2014). According to McCarthy, AI is defined as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs. It is related to the similar task of using computers to understand human intelligence, but AI does not have to confine itself to methods that are biologically observable." In this context, intelligence is perceived as "the computational part of the ability to achieve goals in the world. Varying kinds and degrees of intelligence occur in people, many animals and some machines" (McCarthy 2007). Some definitions emphasize the rationality of machines. Russell et al. define AI as follows: "AI is concerned mainly with rational action. An ideal intelligent agent takes the best possible action in a situation" (Russell/Norvig 2021: p. 52). Others, such as Manning, place greater emphasis on machines being human-like. From his perspective, AI is defined as "machine[s] that can learn, at least somewhat like human beings do" (Manning 2020).

Often, the Turing Test is mentioned as a method to determine whether a machine can be considered intelligent. In this test, a human asks questions and receives multiple answers, both from machines and real humans. If the questioner cannot reliably distinguish between the answers, the machine is considered intelligent. However, the Turing Test is somewhat controversial regarding its effectiveness in identifying "intelligent" systems (IBM n.d.-b).

Additionally, it is important to note that AI has matured significantly in recent years. Consequently, the definition of AI has adapted to address new and more complex tasks that have arisen due to advancements in computational power and a deeper, more refined understanding of AI concepts and methodologies (Russell/Norvig 2021: p. 53).

In general, many official organisations and leading researchers lack in their ability to define what intelligence truly is. Thus, a clear and straight definition is often only given for the word "artificial" but not for the word "intelligence". Often, an intelligent system is defined as intelligent in the comparison to other intelligences, for example humans.

3.4 Machine Learning (ML)

"Machine learning is a subfield of AI that studies the ability to improve performance based on experience. Some AI systems use machine learning methods to achieve competence, but some do not" (Russell/Norvig 2021: p. 19). Manning describes machine learning as "the part of AI studying how computer agents can improve their perception, knowledge, thinking, or actions based on experience or data. For this, Machine Learning (ML) draws from computer science, statistics, psychology, neuroscience, economics and control theory" (Manning 2020). In short "Machine learning [is] the ability to learn without explicitly being programmed" (Amini 2024b).

ML can predict a category for an example based on a labelled dataset, recognize patterns in an unlabelled dataset, forecast trends from data and more. A simple example of this would be linear regression (IBM n.d.-a).

The types of ML are distinguished in supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning. In supervised learning, the algorithm is provided with a dataset where each example contains multiple features and corresponding labels. The model learns from this dataset to predict the label of new, unseen data. The availability of a validated dataset minimizes prediction errors. In contrast, unsupervised learning works with datasets that do not contain labelled examples. The algorithm creates a feature vector¹ for each example, to identify patterns or structure in the data. It transforms the original vector representation into a lower-dimensional vector representation and for instance to assign them to clusters. Semi-supervised learning involves datasets that include both labelled and unlabelled examples, with the unlabelled examples being far more. This approach leverages the information in the unlabelled data to improve learning efficiency. Reinforcement learning is another branch of ML, where the machine learns from its own actions by receiving rewards and penalties. Through this feedback, it develops a policy to solve practical problems (Burkov 2019).

Such ML algorithms, where the "algorithm learns the parameters of the model directly from the features of the training examples", are sometimes called shallow neural networks. These neural networks have only an input and an output layer (Burkov 2019).

¹ "A feature vector is a vector in which each dimension [...] contains a value that describes the example somehow. That value is called a feature" (Burkov 2019).

3.5 Deep Learning (DL)

In contrast, deep neural networks (DNNs) have at least one hidden layer between the input and the output layer. Thus, at least one hidden layer is processing data (Burkov 2019).

Deep Learning (DL) is a subset of Machine Learning (ML). The architectures built in this field are called deep neural networks (DNNs). A successfully trained DNN is called a deep learning model or, in short, a “model” (IBM 2023). DNNs are inspired by the neural networks of the human brain and are currently the most successful ML approach (Manning 2020). (Manning 2020).

Deep learning is the process of “extract[ing] patterns from data using neural networks”. It is heavily dependent on data as well as parallel computing, requiring access to high-performance GPUs for both training and use of a trained model (Amini 2024b).

In this chapter, a feedforward neural network (FFNN) with one input layer, one hidden layer, and one output layer is described as a basic form of a deep neural network (DNN).

A DNN consists of multiple layers containing multiple nodes, also called neurons. Each node connects to others and has its own associated weight and bias. An activation function is applied, and the result is passed to the next layer. This can be seen in Figure 1 (IBM n.d.-d; Amini 2024b).

Fig. 1: Structure of a feedforward neural network (Amini 2024b)

Each node receives multiple inputs. Each input is multiplied by an assigned weight and summed together. A bias is then added. This result is passed through a non-linear activation function and forwarded to the next layer. Connections associated with larger weights have a greater influence on the result than those with smaller weights. This is illustrated in Figure 2 (IBM n.d.-d; Amini 2024b).

Inputs Weights Sum Non-Linearity Output

Fig. 2: Structure of a Neuron in a FFNN (Amini 2024b)

Activation functions determine how the result is passed forward. An activation function is typically a simple non-linear function, as most real-world data is not linear. To illustrate, a linear regression function would be insufficient for modelling non-linear data. The most commonly used activation functions can be seen in Figure 3 (Amini 2024b; IBM n.d.-d).

Fig. 3: Common activation functions in a FFNN (Amini 2024b)

A DNN is trained by updating the weights of its nodes based on training data. Its layer structure is typically designed by a human, and the network starts with randomly initialized weights. It then learns by processing data from the dataset. The input data is passed through the initialized nodes to generate a predicted output. This output is compared to the expected result, and the weights of the relevant nodes are adjusted accordingly. This process, known as backpropagation, which is applied iteratively to each data point in the dataset, with the primary objective to minimize the loss function during training (Amini 2024b).

Deep learning is a relatively old technique, but due to its heavy reliance on parallel computing, it has been gaining increasing attention as GPU technology continues to improve in performance (Amini 2024b).

4 Methods

In this chapter, parametric design methods for creating constructional drawings are presented. Grasshopper is introduced as a widely used example of rule-based methods. In the field of deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) will be examined, specifically within the framework of a conditional adversarial neural network (cGAN).

The key difference between rule-based methods and deep learning methods is, that rule-based methods require a user to explicitly define rules, while deep learning allows users to provide a dataset in which rules have already been applied. From this dataset, the underlying rules, also referred to as patterns, are extracted. The resulting model of such a training process can then apply these patterns to new data (Amini 2024b).

4.1 Rule-Based Methods

4.1.1 Grasshopper (GH)

Grasshopper is a visual scripting language embedded within the CAD Software Rhino (Rhinoceros). Rhino is a versatile, non-industry-specific CAD software that enables the modelling of meshes, NURBS (Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines), and Sub-D (Subdivision Surfaces). It is developed by Robert McNeel & Associates (Harmon 2024; McNeel & Associates n.d.-a)

Grasshopper allows users to program models in 3D space (Harmon 2024; McNeel & Associates n.d.-b). It supports the execution of Python scripts and is widely used for parametric design including parametric construction details. However, parametric rules defined in a Grasshopper script are strict (Rosin 2025; Design-to-Production n.d.).

McNeel & Associates, the company behind Rhino, has cultivated a developer-friendly environment and actively supports third party developers in creating plugins for their software. This has led to the development of numerous custom tools for parametric design by third-party developers (McNeel & Associates n.d.-a; McNeel Europe n.d.).

With the introduction of the function Rhino.Outside, Rhino and Grasshopper can be run embedded within host software, allowing many companies to integrate Rhino- and Grasshopper-functions in their workflow. Rhino.Outside is available for CAD programs like Revit, AutoCAD, and Cadwork, among others (McNeel & Associates n.d.-b; Cadwork Informatik Software GmbH n.d.). Rhino.Outside Cadwork is particularly relevant for wood construction companies, as Cadwork is widely used in this industry. (Rosin 2025).

4.2 Deep Learning Methods

4.2.1 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

CNNs are widely used in computer vision for tasks such as detecting anomalies in radiology images, lane detection in automotive vehicles, and identifying people in images. In contrast to manual feature extraction, a CNN learns its own filters, allowing for more complex recognition. A CNN is built from three main types of layers: convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers² (IBM n.d.-c; Amini 2024a).

It begins with a convolutional layer, which detects features in an image by applying filters. The filter parameters can be regarded as the learned weights. Typically, filters have a 3 × 3 matrix shape that moves across the image, performing matrix multiplication (dot product) between pixel and filter values. Each position where a filter is applied can be considered a node. For an RGB image, each filter has 9 learnable parameters per channel, resulting in 27 parameters per filter. The resulting output matrix is called a feature map. A nonlinear activation function, such as ReLU or Tanh, is then applied elementwise to this feature map, filtering out less significant values. Each convolutional layer contains multiple filters, enabling the network to capture various features in an image at different levels of detail. The more filters are used, the deeper the network becomes (IBM n.d.-c; Amini 2024a). This process can be seen in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Applying a convolutional filter on an image (IBM n.d.-c)

To reduce the dimensions of the calculated feature maps, while retaining the key information, a convolutional layer is usually followed by a pooling layer. The commonly used pooling operation, max-pooling, reduces the matrix size by selecting the highest value within a region of a feature map. Another approach, called average-pooling, calculates the average of the selected region (IBM n.d.-c; Amini 2024a).

² A fully connected layer is a layer in which each node from the previous layer is connected to every node in the fully connected layer (Amini 2024b).

After the initial convolutional and pooling layers, additional convolutional and pooling layers refine the feature extraction process. Early convolutional layers capture fine details like edges, middle layers detect for instance textures, and later layers detect broader patterns, such as objects or people. Through this process the CNN builds a hierarchical understanding of the image. The number of layers chosen for the network architecture depends on the complexity of the task the network is expected to perform and whether the features it needs to extract are fine or broad (IBM n.d.-c; Amini 2024a).

The CNN concludes with a fully connected layer followed by an activation function, like SoftMax or Sigmoid, to process the extracted features and assign the image to a specific class or determine whether a particular object is present (IBM n.d.-c; Amini 2024a).

The structure of a CNN is illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Structure of a convolutional neural network

4.2.2 Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGAN)

A GAN is a general concept, and its architecture depends on the specific application. It is used to generate realistic-looking synthetic data based on conditional inputs. A GAN consists of two competing neural networks: the generator and the discriminator. The generator aims to create data that appear realistic, while the discriminator evaluates the provided data as real or fake (Bhattiprolu 2021a; Lei 2019; Hansen 2022).

In the context of text-to-image translation, a subcategory of GAN is used: the conditional GAN (cGAN). In this case, data is generated based on a condition. This allows the creation of images based on a specified input, such as a textual label (Bhattiprolu 2021a).

The process begins with the generator producing an image based on a given textual label and random noise. The generated images are then mixed with real images from a dataset, and the discriminator attempts to classify them correctly. As the loss from each network is used to update its own weights, both networks improve through training. Once they are sufficiently trained, the desired model is saved. This training process is illustrated in Figure 6 (Bhattiprolu 2021a; Lei 2019; Hansen 2022).

The discriminator typically consists of standard CNN layers, including convolutional layers, normalization layers, and activation functions. In contrast, the generator also uses normalization layers and activation functions but employs transposed convolutional layers instead of standard convolutional layers, effectively reversing the process (Hansen 2022).

Compared to other image generation approaches that integrate two networks, cGANs tend to be less stable, particularly in comparison to other image generating methods, like Variational Autoencoders (VAEs). However, cGANs generally produce more precise images (Bergmann/Stryker 2024).

Fig. 6: Flowchart of a cGAN training process, based on a graphic by (Bhattiprolu 2021a)

Applications for cGANs vary, as the conditional data does not necessarily need to be text. For example, Pix2Pix³ uses images as conditional data, performing image-to-image translation. This can, among others, generate aerial views from satellite images. Other applications of cGANs include semantic-image-to-photo translation, super-resolution image prediction, photo inpainting, video prediction, 3D object generation, and much more (Tensorflow.org 2024b; Brownlee 2019). Although current applications are largely image-based, cGANs hold the potential for much broader use in other domains. “We have only tapped the surface of the true potential of GAN. More and creative use cases will come” (Lei 2019).

At the same time, the rapid improving of GANs raises ethical concerns, as they can be used to generate deepfakes, which have the potential to be misused and may cause harm. The rapid improvement in recent years is shown in Figure 7 (Brundage et al. 2018).

Fig. 7: Evolution of GANs generating deepfakes (Brundage et al. 2018)

³ The name of a cGAN that performs image-to-image translation.

5 Development

Fig. 8: Architectural context

This chapter describes the development process of a digital tool for automatically generating construction drawings.

As the first constructional drawing to be generated by a cGAN, a wall-section was chosen as an example. It has relatively low complexity, thus making it easier to generate a synthetic dataset.

Accordingly, a synthetic dataset of unique wall sections, each with associated dimensions, is created. Although the dataset is artificial and abstract, it provides sufficient variety for the cGAN to capture the underlying relationships between the drawings and dimensions. Ultimately, the goal is to develop a tool that translates a new set of dimensions into a wall section drawing. The process is illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 9: Idea of development

5.1 Dataset

5.1.1 Setup and Requirements

Hardware

- CPU Intel Xeon CPU E3-1270 V2 @ 3.50GHz
- GPU NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti (11GB VRAM)
- RAM 16 GB DDR3 @ 1600MHz

Software

- Operating System Microsoft Windows 10 Pro
- CAD Software Rhino 8 SR15 2025-1-19
- Python 3.9.10

Python Libraries

- NumPy 2.0.2
- Pillow 10.4.0
- OpenCV-Python 4.10.0

5.1.2 Creation Process

The dataset is generated using four separately working Python 3 scripts inside Grasshopper. The Python scripts are written and run within Grasshopper, as they were initially depending on some native Grasshopper components during development.

The dataset generation process follows these steps:

- Create the file "material_colours.csv"
- Create the file "material_dimensions.csv"
- Execute the "Create Variant List" component
- Execute the "Map Dimensions" component
- Execute the "Generate PNG/NPZ" component
- Verify the generated PNGs or use the "Show NPZ File Images" component to inspect the images stored in the NPZ file.

Each component serves a specific function, and the results can be easily verified.

Figure 10 illustrates the dataset generation process:

Fig. 10: Structure of dataset generation process

The following section provides a detailed explanation of the dataset generation process:

Create the file "material_colours.csv"

This file assigns each material to a colour in RGB format, which is used to represent the material in the images. Table 1 below shows the file "material_colours.csv", which was used to create the dataset.

Material_name	red	green	blue
facade	245	116	42
h_battens	162	42	245
v_battens	42	245	244
facade_membrane	97	67	117
Tongue_groove_boarding	163	120	95
Studs_Insulation	218	245	42
Three_layer_board	69	117	117

Tab. 1: CSV file "material_colours.csv"

Create the file "material_dimensions.csv"

This file assigns each material dimensions (thicknesses) in which it is typically fabricated and used in construction. The dimensions are given in millimeters, as each millimeter is corresponding to a pixel in the dataset. Table 2 presents the file "material_dimensions.csv", which was used to generate the dataset.

facade	h_battens	v_battens	facade_membrane	Tongue_groove_boarding	Studs_Insulation	Three_layer_board
14	20	20	1	14	100	16
16	25	25	2	16	101	19
18	30	30		18	102	22
19	40	40		19	103	25
21				21	104	30
24				24	105	40
28				28	106	
32				32	107	
38				38	108	
...
					290	

Tab. 2: CSV file "material_dimensions.csv"

Execute the "Create Variant List" component

The component receives two input parameters:

- the number of desired rows
- the requested batch size

When the component is run, it reads the file "material_dimensions.csv" and randomly generates combinations of material dimensions. Thus, each variant is composed of the same material but with different dimensions. After generation, the component ensures the uniqueness of each variant or rather its dimension combination.

After that, the component stores the variant number and the index of each selected dimension in a separate CSV file per batch.

Table 3 below shows an extract from "variant_list_batch_0.csv," which contains 3,000 variants. The first column, which displays the variant number, is shaded to enhance clarity and comprehension.

variant	facade	h_battens	v_battens	facade_ membrane	Tongue_ groove_ boarding	Studs_ Insulation	Three_ layer_ board
0	4	0	3	1	6	29	4
1	4	2	3	1	1	84	4
2	4	1	3	1	2	79	0
3	3	3	0	1	8	77	0
4	4	1	1	0	1	4	1
5	5	0	1	0	8	78	1
6	3	2	2	0	0	20	3
7	1	1	3	1	2	157	5
...
2999	3	3	3	1	3	7	5

Tab. 3: Extract from CSV file "variant_list_batch_0.csv"

Execute the "Map Dimensions" component

This component reads each variant list CSV file and translates the saved dimension index numbers from each cell into actual dimensions using "material_dimensions.csv" as translator file.

The resulting translated file is saved as "variant_dimensions_batch_0.csv", which corresponds to the input file "variant_list_batch_0.csv".

An extract from the file "variant_dimensions_batch_0.csv" is shown in Table 4.

variant	facade	h_battens	v_battens	facade_ membrane	Tongue_ groove_ boarding	Studs_ Insulation	Three_ layer_board
0	21	20	40	2	28	129	30
1	21	30	40	2	16	184	30
2	21	25	40	2	18	179	16
3	19	40	20	2	38	177	16
4	21	25	25	1	16	104	19
5	24	20	25	1	38	178	19
6	19	30	30	1	14	120	25
7	16	25	40	2	18	257	40
...
2999	19	40	40	2	19	107	40

Tab. 4: Extract from CSV file "variant_dimensions_batch_0.csv"

Execute the "Generate PNG/NPZ" component

This component converts each variant's dimension CSV file into visual images.

An image size of 512 × 512 pixels was chosen because, as a power-of-2 matrix, it allows for efficient GPU processing. Each pixel in the background is assigned the RGB value 0,0,0 representing pure black.

The "Generate PNG/NPZ" component functions as follows: First, it calculates the position and dimensions of each material and retrieves the corresponding material colour. To apply a black margin at the image border, the position is shifted by 10 pixels perpendicular to the wall. After this adjustment, a rectangle is drawn at the determined location. This process repeats for each material until the entire variant is rendered. Finally, the image is saved with the variant number in the filename.

Additionally, the component generates a compressed NumPy file (NPZ) containing all images of one batch. A unique feature of this NPZ file is that each image includes a fourth channel,

which stores the variant number in addition to the standard RGB channels. The resulting array structure is further explained in Chapter 6: Results.

For optimized performance, this component employs multi-threading.

Verify the generated Images

The Component "Show NPZ File Images" was developed to inspect the images saved as an NPZ file. It takes an NPZ file path as input along with a specific range of variant numbers to be examined. The component then utilizes OpenCV to visualize the selected images.

ML-optimized dataset

Additionally, the potential of an ML-optimized dataset using the ML plugin "Opossum" was successfully tested but ultimately discarded, since an optimized dataset was not considered necessary. This approach was not pursued further. A detailed explanation is provided in Chapter 7: Conclusion.

5.2 Digital Tool

5.2.1 Setup and Requirements

Hardware

- CPU Intel Xeon E3-1270 V2 @ 3.50GHz
- GPU NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti
- RAM 16 GB DDR3 @ 1600MHz

GPU Dependencies

- GPU Driver Studio Driver 566.36
- CUDA 12.3
- cuDNN 8.9.7

Software

- Operating System Microsoft Windows 10 Pro
- Spyder 6.0.1
- Python 3.12.8

Libraries

- Keras 3.4.1
- TensorFlow 2.17.0
- Matplotlib 3.9.2
- NumPy 1.26.4

5.2.2 Creation Process

A code written by Bhattiprolu, based on a code by Jason Brownlee, was used as the basis for cGAN training. Bhattiprolu's code is included in the appendix. In his implementation, TensorFlow 2.4.1 and Keras 2.4.3 were used (Bhattiprolu 2021b). However, due to installation failures with these specific versions, the latest stable versions available at the time were installed in an Anaconda environment: TensorFlow 2.17.0, Keras 3.4.1, and other dependencies as listed in Chapter 5.2.1 Requirements.

Bhattiprolu's code uses the CIFAR-10 dataset as a testing dataset. This approach was adopted here, initially training the cGAN on CIFAR-10 to ensure that a reliable training process could be achieved. The CIFAR-10 dataset consists of 60,000 labelled images, each with a resolution of 32×32 pixels. The labels include airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse,

ship, and truck. This dataset is widely used for testing and evaluating model performance (Krizhevsky et al. n.d.).

Unfortunately, running the code of Bhattiprolu with newer versions of TensorFlow and Keras resulted in a few problems:

- Starting from Keras 3.0, the "alpha" parameter in the LeakyReLU (Leaky Rectified Linear Unit) activation function was renamed to "negative_slope", though its functionality remains unchanged.
- Starting from Keras 3.0, the "lr" parameter in the Adam optimizer was renamed to "learning_rate".

After correcting this in the code, it ran partially successfully, as it only operated on the CPU and did not utilize the GPU at all. Additionally, TensorFlow regularly output an error at fixed intervals:

```
2025-02-04 20:29:36.643069: E tensorflow/core/grappler/optimizers/meta_optimizer.cc:966] remapper failed: INVALID_ARGUMENT: Mutation::Apply error: fanout 'StatefulPartitionedCall/gradient_tape/functional_4_1/functional_2_1/leaky_re_lu_6_1/LeakyRelu/LeakyReluGrad' exist for missing node 'StatefulPartitionedCall/functional_4_1/functional_2_1/conv2d_4_1/add'.
```

At the beginning of the training, this error message occurred after every 12th batch. Just before TensorFlow automatically terminated the training process, the error appeared every 4th batch. The error suggests that TensorFlow failed to optimize the computational graph during backpropagation, likely due to missing nodes. Since the training was running exclusively on the CPU, VRAM limitations could not have been the cause.

To investigate potential memory issues, the batch size was reduced to 32 and then to 8, while monitoring RAM usage for any overflow. However, even though sufficient RAM space was available, and the error persisted even with smaller batch sizes. This indicates that the issue is more likely related to the training process itself or incompatibilities between packages. The fact that the error occurs even early in the training process supports this assumption further. Possible approaches to address this issue are discussed in Chapter 8: Further Research.

Due to these compatibility issues, alternative methods for setting up a functional cGAN training environment with GPU support were explored. It was discovered that TensorFlow no longer provides GPU support on native Windows starting from TensorFlow 2.11 (Tensorflow.org 2024a). Alternative environment solutions for TensorFlow working on native Windows are discussed in Chapter 8: Further Research.

6 Results

This thesis investigated the use of Deep Neural Networks for the development of CAD applications, particularly CNNs within the framework of a cGAN. An initial understanding of AI learning processes, generative AI techniques, and AI-based computer vision was established. A pathway for developing a digital tool capable of automatically generating constructional details was identified. To achieve this, a dataset was synthesized, and the cGAN training process was initiated. This Chapter presents the results obtained.

Dataset

A synthetic dataset of 60,000 randomly assembled wall-sections was generated, ensuring the uniqueness of each variant. The dataset was saved in 20 batches, in 3,000 variants per batch. Each variant was stored as an RGB image in a PNG file, as well each batch as an NPZ file.

The component creation process, as described in Chapter 5.1.2, took:

- 0.957 seconds to create the variant list
- 0.630 seconds to map dimensions
- 4.5 minutes to generate PNG files
- 9.6 minutes to generate NPZ files

The generated images have a resolution of 512×512 pixels, as this matrix size, being a power of 2, enables efficient processing with common GPUs. Additionally, it was ensured that the layering of materials in the dataset images starts with a padding of 10 pixels. This prevents the loss of edge information for a cGAN trained on this dataset.

Below, Variant 654 of Batch 0 from the dataset is displayed as an example. An extract from a representative part of the "variant_dimensions.csv" file is provided (Table 5), followed by the synthesized image (Figure 11) and its corresponding constructional drawing (Figure 12). The CSV file serves as the label data for a cGAN trained on this dataset.

variant	facade	h_battens	v_battens	facade_ membrane	Tongue_ groove_ boarding	Studs_ Insulation	Three_ layer_ board
...
654	24	30	30	1	24	283	25
...

Tab. 5: Extract from CSV file "variant_dimensions_batch_0.csv" showing variant 654

Fig. 11: Generated image of variant 654

Fig. 12: Corresponding detail of variant 654

As mentioned, in addition to the PNG files, each batch was stored as an NPZ file for efficient storage and quick loading during the cGAN training process. The use of NPZ files enables the storage of all variant images in a single compressed file, avoiding the need for thousands of individual PNG files. This improves the efficiency in handling the data. The structure of an NPZ file is illustrated in Figure 13.

Fig. 13: Data structure of NPZ files

In addition to the randomly generated dataset, an approach for creating an ML-optimized dataset was successfully tested but not further explored. However, this approach could become relevant in the future as larger and more complex datasets are collected and training times need to be optimized.

Digital Tool

Initially, numerous version and package compatibility issues occurred. Once these were resolved, training could only be executed on a CPU, but it remained partially unstable. At the beginning of the training, TensorFlow failed every 12th batch while optimizing the model during backpropagation. Over time, these failures occurred at increasingly shorter intervals, eventually leading to an automatic termination by TensorFlow. Just before termination, every 4th batch produced the following repeated error message:

```
2025-02-04 20:29:36.643069: E tensorflow/core/grappler/optimizers/meta_optimizer.cc:966]
remapper failed: INVALID_ARGUMENT: Mutation::Apply error: fanout
'StatefulPartitionedCall/gradient_tape/functional_4_1/functional_2_1/leaky_re_lu_6_1/LeakyR
elu/LeakyReluGrad' exist for missing node
'StatefulPartitionedCall/functional_4_1/functional_2_1/conv2d_4_1/add'.
```

The longest training run on the CIFAR-10 dataset lasted for 4 epochs⁴ and 292 batches, before TensorFlow automatically terminated the process. Unfortunately, the model was not saved just before the termination.

However, a model trained for 2 epochs was successfully saved. This model was used to generate 100 images, each 32×32 pixels, with 10 images per label, as in the CIFAR-10 dataset. These are displayed in Figure 14.

Fig. 14: Training results on CIFAR-10 after 2 epochs

As expected, the generated images do not clearly depict recognizable objects corresponding to their labels, such as birds, cats, or dogs. This outcome is not surprising, as 2 epochs are insufficient for a meaningful training progress.

Successfully training a cGAN with the synthesised dataset of wall-sections was not attempted, as general training issues need to be resolved first.

⁴ An epoch is a complete cycle through the dataset during model training (Brownlee 2022).

7 Conclusion

DNNs can generate highly complex data within the range of the provided dataset. Text-to-Image cGANs have the potential to learn the relationships between textual input to the arrangement and connection of building components, as well as the relationship of textual input to the building components' dimensions. This could lead to models capable of generating constructional drawings in general, based on text. A trained model would not be constrained by human-designed predefined arrangements, as seen in most Grasshopper scripts of constructional details. However, the performance of a cGAN is highly dependent on the dataset and the computational power available for training and execution of the model.

A cGAN model was trained for 2 epochs on the CIFAR-10 dataset and was not trained on the synthetic dataset of wall-sections. This was due to multiple technical issues encountered during the setup of the training environment, as well as instability of the cGAN during training on CIFAR-10. A deeper understanding of the training process is essential before a cGAN can be effectively trained. Additionally, a well-set-up training environment is needed before meaningful results can be achieved and a more profound assessment of the cGAN's capabilities can be made.

The process of creating a synthetic dataset could be programmed more efficiently, but since the current implementation performs its intended function, there is no immediate need for changes. The image size of the synthesized dataset could be reduced far more to a linear image format. This would significantly reduce the need for computational power and enhance the training efficiency. Further validation of the dataset is required, as it was previously checked only through a brief manual inspection.

The synthesis of an ML-optimized dataset was successfully tested but was eventually considered unnecessary. A cGAN trained on an optimized dataset would be more confident in generating high-performance wall-sections while being less reliable in generating low-performing wall-sections. Additionally, the question remains as to which characteristic the dataset should be optimized for. Nonetheless, ML-optimized datasets could become relevant in the future, when larger and more complex datasets are collected, and training times need to be optimized.

Optimization should be considered separately from the method used to generate constructional details. Both cGANs and Grasshopper define the design range of a constructional detail, but cGANs potentially have the advantage of defining the relationship and connection between the generated building components autonomously. In contrast, constructional details defined through a Grasshopper script rely on the human-defined

relationships between building components. Regardless, both approaches define complex interdependencies among building components and both methods could be used within the optimization of the constructional details.

A synthesized dataset created through rule-based methods is sufficient for an initial proof of concept. However, a model trained on this dataset will only learn the predefined rules used to generate it. To create additional value in the future, a dataset of real constructional drawings is necessary.

Regardless of how a dataset of real construction details is obtained, it is expected that a single type of detail will not be available in dimensional variations, such as a roof edge detail with different insulation thicknesses. Therefore, a real-world dataset could be supplemented with a synthetic dataset. This synthetic dataset should include a few construction details, each in multiple dimensional variations to induce dimensional variability. Achieving this could mark a milestone: transferring knowledge of dimensional changes to a new construction detail. As always, the output of a generated detail should be defined by a given textual input. This concept is illustrated in Figure 15.

Fig. 15: Transferring knowledge of dimensional variability

To achieve this, an appropriate structure for providing the model with the textual (conditional) data must be found, as the more complex the constructional details are that the cGAN is trained on, the more complex the textual description needs to be in order to accurately describe the desired constructional detail.

While cGANs are typically applied to 2D images, they can be applied to data in any dimension without limitation. A cGAN can be trained on 1D sections, 2D constructional details, or even 3D constructions, as long as an appropriate dataset is available.

8 Further Research

This Chapter outlines promising directions for future research, structured in a logical sequence, as some build up on previous ones.

a) Set Up a Well-Configured cGAN Training Environment

To address challenges of establishing a training environment with GPU acceleration on native Windows, a Docker container within WSL2 (Windows Subsystem for Linux 2) appears to be an initial solution. This approach has been briefly tested. Steps to take:

- Ensure the latest GPU drivers are installed.
- Enable WSL 2.
- Set up a Docker container with GPU support.
- Install CUDA and cuDNN (CUDA Toolkit) inside the Docker container. This requires an NVIDIA graphics card. CUDA must be compatible with the GPU drivers.
- Run TensorFlow in a Docker container.

Additional resources and links for configuring this environment are provided in the appendix under 11.2: Resources for Setting Up cGAN Training Environment.

The next steps should also include evaluating the resources required for effective training and adjusting the hardware accordingly. The required resources may be reduced by optimizing the training process. However, a workstation with a capable NVIDIA GPU appears necessary for obtaining meaningful results. If more advanced resources become necessary, computing time can be applied from data centres. The Linux cluster at the University of Kassel may provide such an option. It is important to note that executing a trained model typically requires significantly fewer resources than training one.

b) Validation of the Synthesized Dataset

As mentioned in Chapter 7 (Conclusion), the generated dataset should receive further validation, as it was previously checked only through a brief manual inspection. To achieve high-quality training results, an accurate validation is necessary.

c) Train a cGAN on a Linear Dataset

As discussed in Chapter 7 (Conclusion), the synthesized dataset's image size could be further reduced to a linear format (potentially 512x1 pixels). This would significantly reduce the computational power needed and would make the training more efficient.

d) Define Structure for Conditional Data

To define an appropriate structure for providing a cGAN with textual data containing multiple conditions, an approach proposed by a Google research team could serve as an inspiration. They used transformer language models to interpret textual prompts and utilized these interpretations to generate images through a guided diffusion model. They achieved remarkable results with this approach. A similar method could enable a cGAN to generate construction details based on free-text descriptions (Saharia et al. 2022).

e) Investigate Guided Diffusion Models and VAEs as Alternative Approaches

Guided diffusion models and variational autoencoders (VAEs) should be explored as potential alternatives to cGANs. In particular, VAEs may be advantageous due to their greater training stability (IBM 2024).

f) Apply Vector Arithmetic to Latent Representations of Generated Data

Vector arithmetic can be used to decompose a construction detail into its fundamental components. Considering a construction detail as a latent vector, the vector of an interior-to-exterior wall connection detail could be separated into an indoor-wall-section vector, an exterior-wall-section vector, and a connection-elements vector. Applying this approach to multiple variations of an interior-to-exterior wall connection detail may enable the recombination of the extracted vectors into new construction details. A testing dataset for this approach could be synthesized using rule-based methods, incorporating variations in the type and dimensions of interior-to-exterior wall connection details.

Radford, Meth et al. (2015) demonstrated the effectiveness of applying vector arithmetic to generated data using the example of portraits of people. This is shown in Figure 16.

Fig. 16: Vector arithmetic for visual concepts (Radford et al. 2015: p. 10)

g) Investigate Training cGANs Directly on Vector Drawings

Developing a setup in which a DNN does not require pixel-based data could be highly advantageous, as it would significantly reduce the amount of data that needs to be processed. However, pixel-based data is generally easier to use than vectorized data in DNNs, as most are specifically designed for such input.

h) Acquire and Structure a Real Dataset of Construction Details

To create future value with this research, a dataset of real construction details is crucial. Such a dataset could be structured using CNNs for semantic segmentation to convert raw, unstructured data into a structured format. This approach, the semantic segmentation of construction plans, has already been demonstrated by researchers (Kim et al. 2021). The resulting dataset could be further augmented by synthetically generated variations of the obtained data, such as “zooming [the image] slightly, rotating, flipping, [or] darkening.” This augmentation process can enhance the performance of a model trained on this dataset (Burkov 2019).

i) Explore Transfer Learning of a cGAN Trained on Real Constructional Details

As noted in Chapter 7 (Conclusion), a dataset of real construction details could be enhanced by adding a few construction details, each with a number of dimensional variations of building components. Since, in real data, a single detail is unlikely to appear in multiple dimensions of the drawn building components, this approach could enable the cGAN to transfer knowledge of dimensional variance to real data, described through textual input. See Figure 15 in Chapter 7 (Conclusion).

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11 Appendix

11.1 Code by Bhattiprolu (2021)

The code by Bhattiprolu (2021) is available at:

https://github.com/bnsreenu/python_for_microscopists/blob/master/249_keras_implementation_of_conditional_GAN/249-cifar_conditional_GAN.py

```
"""
```

```
Based on the code by Jason Brownlee from his blogs on https://machinelearningmastery.com/  
I seriously urge everyone to follow his blogs and get enlightened.  
I am adapting his code to various applications but original credit goes to Jason.
```

```
Conditional GAN that generates images using a random latent vector and corresponding label  
as input.
```

```
Conditional GANs can be used to supply a label during training so the latent vector  
can be associated with a specific label - making the generation of images predictable.
```

```
Following code trains and generates images based on the mnist digits dataset.
```

```
"""
```

```
from numpy import zeros  
from numpy import ones  
from numpy.random import randn  
from numpy.random import randint  
from keras.datasets.cifar10 import load_data  
from keras.optimizers import Adam  
from keras.models import Model  
from keras.layers import Input  
from keras.layers import Dense  
from keras.layers import Reshape  
from keras.layers import Flatten  
from keras.layers import Conv2D  
from keras.layers import Conv2DTranspose  
from keras.layers import LeakyReLU  
from keras.layers import Dropout  
from keras.layers import Embedding  
from keras.layers import Concatenate  
  
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt  
#####  
  
#Load data and plot to get a quick understanding  
#CIFAR10 classes are: airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse,  
# ship, truck  
  
(trainX, trainy), (testX, testy) = load_data()  
  
# plot 25 images  
for i in range(25):  
    plt.subplot(5, 5, 1 + i)  
    plt.axis('off')  
    plt.imshow(trainX[i])  
plt.show()
```

```

#####
#Define generator, discriminator, gan and other helper functions
#We will use functional way of defining model as we have multiple inputs;
#both images and corresponding labels.
#####

# define the standalone discriminator model
#Given an input image, the Discriminator outputs the likelihood of the image being real.
#Binary classification - true or false (1 or 0). So using sigmoid activation.

#Unlike regular GAN here we are also providing number of classes as input.
#Input to the model will be both images and labels.
def define_discriminator(in_shape=(32,32,3), n_classes=10):

    # label input
    in_label = Input(shape=(1,)) #Shape 1
    # embedding for categorical input
    #each label (total 10 classes for cifar), will be represented by a vector of size 50.
    #This vector of size 50 will be learnt by the discriminator
    li = Embedding(n_classes, 50)(in_label) #Shape 1,50
    # scale up to image dimensions with linear activation
    n_nodes = in_shape[0] * in_shape[1] #32x32 = 1024.
    li = Dense(n_nodes)(li) #Shape = 1, 1024
    # reshape to additional channel
    li = Reshape((in_shape[0], in_shape[1], 1))(li) #32x32x1

    # image input
    in_image = Input(shape=in_shape) #32x32x3
    # concat label as a channel
    merge = Concatenate()(in_image, li) #32x32x4 (4 channels, 3 for image and the other for
    labels)

    # downsample: This part is same as unconditional GAN upto the output layer.
    #We will combine input label with input image and supply as inputs to the model.
    fe = Conv2D(128, (3,3), strides=(2,2), padding='same')(merge) #16x16x128
    fe = LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2)(fe)
    # downsample
    fe = Conv2D(128, (3,3), strides=(2,2), padding='same')(fe) #8x8x128
    fe = LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2)(fe)
    # flatten feature maps
    fe = Flatten()(fe) #8192 (8*8*128=8192)
    # dropout
    fe = Dropout(0.4)(fe)
    # output
    out_layer = Dense(1, activation='sigmoid')(fe) #Shape=1

    # define model
    ##Combine input label with input image and supply as inputs to the model.
    model = Model([in_image, in_label], out_layer)
    # compile model
    opt = Adam(lr=0.0002, beta_1=0.5)
    model.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=opt, metrics=['accuracy'])
    return model

test_discr = define_discriminator()
print(test_discr.summary())

# define the standalone generator model
#latent vector and label as inputs

def define_generator(latent_dim, n_classes=10):

    # label input
    in_label = Input(shape=(1,)) #Input of dimension 1
    # embedding for categorical input
    #each label (total 10 classes for cifar), will be represented by a vector of size 50.

```

```

li = Embedding(n_classes, 50)(in_label) #Shape 1,50

# linear multiplication
n_nodes = 8 * 8 # To match the dimensions for concatenation later in this step.
li = Dense(n_nodes)(li) #1,64
# reshape to additional channel
li = Reshape((8, 8, 1))(li)

# image generator input
in_lat = Input(shape=(latent_dim,)) #Input of dimension 100

# foundation for 8x8 image
# We will reshape input latent vector into 8x8 image as a starting point.
#So n_nodes for the Dense layer can be 128x8x8 so when we reshape the output
#it would be 8x8x128 and that can be slowly upsampled to 32x32 image for output.
#Note that this part is same as unconditional GAN until the output layer.
#While defining model inputs we will combine input label and the latent input.
n_nodes = 128 * 8 * 8
gen = Dense(n_nodes)(in_lat) #shape=8192
gen = LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2)(gen)
gen = Reshape((8, 8, 128))(gen) #Shape=8x8x128
# merge image gen and label input
merge = Concatenate()(gen, li) #Shape=8x8x129 (Extra channel corresponds to the label)
# upsample to 16x16
gen = Conv2DTranspose(128, (4,4), strides=(2,2), padding='same')(merge) #16x16x128
gen = LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2)(gen)
# upsample to 32x32
gen = Conv2DTranspose(128, (4,4), strides=(2,2), padding='same')(gen) #32x32x128
gen = LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2)(gen)
# output
out_layer = Conv2D(3, (8,8), activation='tanh', padding='same')(gen) #32x32x3
# define model
model = Model([in_lat, in_label], out_layer)
return model #Model not compiled as it is not directly trained like the discriminator.

test_gen = define_generator(100, n_classes=10)
print(test_gen.summary())

# #Generator is trained via GAN combined model.
# define the combined generator and discriminator model, for updating the generator
#Discriminator is trained separately so here only generator will be trained by keeping
#the discriminator constant.
def define_gan(g_model, d_model):
    d_model.trainable = False #Discriminator is trained separately. So set to not trainable.

    ## connect generator and discriminator...
    # first, get noise and label inputs from generator model
    gen_noise, gen_label = g_model.input #Latent vector size and label size
    # get image output from the generator model
    gen_output = g_model.output #32x32x3

    # generator image output and corresponding input label are inputs to discriminator
    gan_output = d_model([gen_output, gen_label])
    # define gan model as taking noise and label and outputting a classification
    model = Model([gen_noise, gen_label], gan_output)
    # compile model
    opt = Adam(lr=0.0002, beta_1=0.5)
    model.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=opt)
    return model

# load cifar images
def load_real_samples():
    # load dataset
    (trainX, trainy), (_, _) = load_data() #cifar
    # convert to floats and scale
    X = trainX.astype('float32')

```

```

# scale from [0,255] to [-1,1]
X = (X - 127.5) / 127.5 #Generator uses tanh activation so rescale
                          #original images to -1 to 1 to match the output of generator.
return [X, trainy]

# # select real samples
# pick a batch of random real samples to train the GAN
#In fact, we will train the GAN on a half batch of real images and another
#half batch of fake images.
#For each real image we assign a label 1 and for fake we assign label 0.
def generate_real_samples(dataset, n_samples):
    # split into images and labels
    images, labels = dataset
    # choose random instances
    ix = randint(0, images.shape[0], n_samples)
    # select images and labels
    X, labels = images[ix], labels[ix]
    # generate class labels and assign to y (don't confuse this with the above labels that
    correspond to cifar labels)
    y = ones((n_samples, 1)) #Label=1 indicating they are real
    return [X, labels], y

# generate points in latent space as input for the generator
def generate_latent_points(latent_dim, n_samples, n_classes=10):
    # generate points in the latent space
    x_input = randn(latent_dim * n_samples)
    # reshape into a batch of inputs for the network
    z_input = x_input.reshape(n_samples, latent_dim)
    # generate labels
    labels = randint(0, n_classes, n_samples)
    return [z_input, labels]

# use the generator to generate n fake examples, with class labels
#Supply the generator, latent_dim and number of samples as input.
#Use the above latent point generator to generate latent points.
def generate_fake_samples(generator, latent_dim, n_samples):
    # generate points in latent space
    z_input, labels_input = generate_latent_points(latent_dim, n_samples)
    # predict outputs
    images = generator.predict([z_input, labels_input])
    # create class labels
    y = zeros((n_samples, 1)) #Label=0 indicating they are fake
    return [images, labels_input], y

# train the generator and discriminator
#We loop through a number of epochs to train our Discriminator by first selecting
#a random batch of images from our true/real dataset.
#Then, generating a set of images using the generator.
#Feed both set of images into the Discriminator.
#Finally, set the loss parameters for both the real and fake images, as well as the combined
loss.
def train(g_model, d_model, gan_model, dataset, latent_dim, n_epochs=100, n_batch=128):
    bat_per_epo = int(dataset[0].shape[0] / n_batch)
    half_batch = int(n_batch / 2) #the discriminator model is updated for a half batch of
real samples
                                #and a half batch of fake samples, combined a single batch.
    # manually enumerate epochs
    for i in range(n_epochs):
        # enumerate batches over the training set
        for j in range(bat_per_epo):

            # Train the discriminator on real and fake images, separately (half batch each)
            #Research showed that separate training is more effective.
            # get randomly selected 'real' samples
            # get randomly selected 'real' samples
            [X_real, labels_real], y_real = generate_real_samples(dataset, half_batch)

```

```

# update discriminator model weights
##train_on_batch allows you to update weights based on a collection
#of samples you provide
d_loss_real, _ = d_model.train_on_batch([X_real, labels_real], y_real)

# generate 'fake' examples
[X_fake, labels], y_fake = generate_fake_samples(g_model, latent_dim, half_batch)
# update discriminator model weights
d_loss_fake, _ = d_model.train_on_batch([X_fake, labels], y_fake)

#d_loss = 0.5 * np.add(d_loss_real, d_loss_fake) #Average loss if you want to
report single..

# prepare points in latent space as input for the generator
[z_input, labels_input] = generate_latent_points(latent_dim, n_batch)

# The generator wants the discriminator to label the generated samples
# as valid (ones)
#This is where the generator is trying to trick discriminator into believing
#the generated image is true (hence value of 1 for y)
# create inverted labels for the fake samples
y_gan = ones((n_batch, 1))
# Generator is part of combined model where it got directly linked with the
discriminator
# Train the generator with latent_dim as x and 1 as y.
# Again, 1 as the output as it is adversarial and if generator did a great
#job of folling the discriminator then the output would be 1 (true)
# update the generator via the discriminator's error
g_loss = gan_model.train_on_batch([z_input, labels_input], y_gan)
# Print losses on this batch
print('Epoch>%d, Batch%d/%d, d1=%.3f, d2=%.3f g=%.3f' %
      (i+1, j+1, bat_per_epo, d_loss_real, d_loss_fake, g_loss))
# save the generator model
g_model.save('cifar_conditional_generator_25epochs.h5')

#Train the GAN

# size of the latent space
latent_dim = 100
# create the discriminator
d_model = define_discriminator()
# create the generator
g_model = define_generator(latent_dim)
# create the gan
gan_model = define_gan(g_model, d_model)
# load image data
dataset = load_real_samples()
# train model
train(g_model, d_model, gan_model, dataset, latent_dim, n_epochs=2)

```

```

#####
# Now, let us load the generator model and generate images
# Load the trained model and generate a few images
from numpy import asarray
from numpy.random import randn
from numpy.random import randint
from keras.models import load_model
import numpy as np
#

#Note: CIFAR10 classes are: airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse,
# ship, truck

# load model
model = load_model('cifar_conditional_generator_250epochs.h5')

# generate multiple images

latent_points, labels = generate_latent_points(100, 100)
# specify labels - generate 10 sets of labels each going from 0 to 9
labels = asarray([x for _ in range(10) for x in range(10)])
# generate images
X = model.predict([latent_points, labels])
# scale from [-1,1] to [0,1]
X = (X + 1) / 2.0
X = (X*255).astype(np.uint8)
# plot the result (10 sets of images, all images in a column should be of same class in the
plot)
# Plot generated images
def show_plot(examples, n):
    for i in range(n * n):
        plt.subplot(n, n, 1 + i)
        plt.axis('off')
        plt.imshow(examples[i, :, :, :])
    plt.show()

show_plot(X, 10)

```

11.2 Resources for Setting Up cGAN Training Environment

Setting Up a WSL Development Environment:

<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/wsl/setup/environment>

WSL Documentation "Get started with GPU acceleration for ML in WSL":

<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/wsl/tutorials/gpu-compute>

Install Docker:

<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/wsl/tutorials/wsl-containers>

NVIDIA Container Toolkit:

<https://docs.nvidia.com/datacenter/cloud-native/container-toolkit/latest/index.html>

TensorFlow Docker installation guide:

<https://www.tensorflow.org/install/docker>

Official TensorFlow Docker Image:

<https://hub.docker.com/r/tensorflow/tensorflow>

Tutorial for setting up "TensorFlow with GPU on Windows WSL using Docker":

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YozfiLI1ogY>

TensorFlow-Guide:

<https://www.tensorflow.org/guide>

Keras-Guide:

https://keras.io/getting_started/

12 Declaration of AI-Usage

The present bachelor's thesis was written in English by me, Stephan Rosin, matriculation number [REDACTED]. AI tools, specifically GPT-4o from OpenAI, were used to correct and improve spelling, grammar, expression, style, cohesion, and readability of a manually written text. The aim was to enhance clarity for the reader without modifying the content of the text. AI was not used to generate any new content.

To achieve this, the AI tool was provided with specific constraints:

In this conversation, I will provide a piece of text for you to correct. I am a student working on my bachelor's thesis. Please correct the spelling, grammar, expression, style, cohesion, wording, clarity, and flow. Make corrections cautiously, gently and carefully. Please ensure the text remains professional and adheres the generally accepted scientific standards. If the text includes a literal citation, do not modify any text within the citation. Format all literal citations in bold so I can review them.

Thereafter, I meticulously reviewed the text to prevent any unintended modifications. I take full responsibility and liability for the published text, ensuring it complies with all scientific standards.

Place, Date

Signature

I asked GPT-4o in a plain chat the question: "How do you understand this instruction?" followed by the constraints from the last page. This was its answer:

This instruction conveys that you are seeking a careful and professional review of your bachelor's thesis text. Here's how I interpret it:

1. **Objective:** To ensure the provided text meets **scientific and academic standards**, maintaining professionalism while improving language and coherence.
2. **Scope of Corrections:**
 - **Spelling and Grammar:** Fix any typographical, grammatical, or punctuation errors.
 - **Expression and Style:** Adjust phrasing to improve readability and align with an academic tone.
 - **Cohesion and Flow:** Improve the logical structure and ensure smooth transitions between sentences and ideas.
 - **Wording and Clarity:** Simplify and refine sentences to avoid ambiguity while maintaining precision.
3. **Careful and Respectful Edits:**
 - Avoid altering the intended meaning.
 - Make changes cautiously, keeping the writer's style and voice intact.
 - Apply corrections "gently," meaning changes should be minimal and only made when necessary to enhance clarity or correctness.
4. **Literal Citations:**
 - **Do not modify** any text within direct quotations or citations to preserve their authenticity.
 - **Mark all citations in bold** for easy identification and review by you.
5. **Tone and Adherence:**
 - All revisions must align with accepted **scientific standards**, such as objectivity, formal language, and logical rigor.
 - Keep the text professional, avoiding colloquial or informal expressions.

In short, I will focus on enhancing your text's quality while respecting its original intent, especially in cited material, which will be highlighted for your verification.

13 Declaration of Authenticity

I, Stephan Rosin, matriculation number [REDACTED], hereby declare that I have written this bachelor's thesis independently, have not submitted it in whole or in part as an examination paper, and have not used any aids other than those specified. I have properly acknowledged all passages taken from sources, whether quoted literally or paraphrased, by providing appropriate citations. Furthermore, I confirm that the printed copies of this thesis are identical to the digital version of the bachelor's thesis submitted in advance.

Ich, Stephan Rosin, Matrikelnummer [REDACTED], versichere hiermit, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig verfasst, ganz oder in Teilen noch nicht als Prüfungsleistung vorgelegt und keine anderen als die angegebenen Hilfsmittel benutzt habe. Sämtliche Stellen der Arbeit, die benutzten Quellen im Wortlaut oder dem Sinn nach entnommen sind, habe ich durch Quellenangaben kenntlich gemacht. Ich versichere ebenso, dass die Papieraufbereitungen der Arbeit identisch mit der vorab versandten digitalen Version der Bachelorarbeit sind.

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